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Full Length Research Paper

An integrated study on the relationship between Benefits Realization Management (BRM) and the National Transformation Program (NTP) in the light of Saudi Arabia Vision 2030

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The Kingdom's Vision 2030 program entered its next phase in 2021 with the National Transformation Program, which included 7 themes and 34 strategic objectives. This research examines the benefits realization management and national transformation programs in Saudi Arabia in the context of the Vision 2030 strategy. The research problem was to investigate how BRM is being realized in the implementation phase of the National Transformation Program (NTP) in order to identify challenges and opportunities associated with its implementation. There is a lack of studies linked between Benefits Realization Management (BRM) and the National Transformation Programs (NTP) in light of Saudi Arabia's Vision. In addition, most of the literature available on the subject of BRM is centred on corporate environments such as IT or development projects in manufacturing or telecom sectors. To reach the desired Benefits Realization Management (BRM), precise, unambiguous objectives must be established, and precise performance indicators to monitor the outcomes and measure the benefits. The National Transformation Program has precise objectives and key performance indicators for each of its seven themes. The researcher evaluates pertinent reports and studies to observe the benefits that have been achieved. The results of the seven themes developed by NTP indicate substantial realized benefits through applying big numbers of initiatives during 2023. The NTP achieved many benefits through the actual implementation of numerous initiatives during the period 2021 to 2025. Indeed, until January 2023, it has gained considerable achievements in the seven themes identified in the National Transformation Program and has introduced several initiatives that will be implemented in the coming period. This integrated approach is expected to lead to better outcomes and enhanced efficiency, especially where programs are coordinated across departments and agencies. The BRM process will continue to help the authorities implement the National Transformation Program effectively.

Keywords: (BRM) Benefits realization management - (NTP) National Transformation Program - (KPIs) Key Performance Indicators. (NAGIZ) judicial services platform- (ETHRAI) Training platform- (WAQFY) donations platform- (QURRAH) childcare services platform - (MOWAAMAH) Programs provide appropriate working conditions for individuals with disabilities.

INTRODUCTION

Benefits realization management (BRM) is a proven and effective methodology that helps organizations realize the potential benefits of their projects, programs, and portfolios. It is a well-established discipline that can be

applied to a wide variety of projects and processes within an organization. It can help companies achieve better performance through more effective project delivery and improved decision-making. That is why it is a

fundamental part of the National Transformation Program (NTP) in Saudi Arabia. Furthermore, it is an important element of the National Transformation Program (NTP) that aims to transform the country into a knowledge-based economy that is globally competitive and technologically innovative. (Khorsheed, 2015). The current study examining the relationship between Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 and Benefits Realization Management (BRM) through examines BRM in the context of the National Transformation Program (NTP -7 themes) in order to understand how BRM can play a role in realizing the goals of Vision 2030 through investigate the benefits from the seven themes developed by NTP.

Research Problem

The research problem was to investigate how BRM is being realized in the implementation phase of the National Transformation Program (NTP) in order to identify challenges and opportunities associated with its implementation. There is a lack of studies linked between Benefits Realization Management (BRM) and the National Transformation Programs (NTP) in light of Saudi Arabia's Vision. In addition, most of the literature available on the subject of BRM is centered on corporate environments such as IT or development projects in manufacturing or telecom sectors.

Research Objectives

The objective of this research is to identify and analyze the benefits realization management (BRM) and national transformation programs (NTP) in Saudi Arabia in the context of its Vision 2030 strategy and to assess the impacts and outcomes of these programs on the Kingdom's development, based on past research and case studies from around the world.

Research Methods

The study used a theoretical approach and data collected from the websites of various government agencies responsible for implementing BRM and NTP in the Kingdom, as well as from literature about BRM and NTP.

Research Limitation

This research is limited to the National Transformation Programs (7 published themes) and its relationship with the realized benefit in KSA. The researcher sought to find out the relationship between BRM and realized benefit in KSA and studied both programs from different perspective through different lenses. Although the research was done from a macro perspective, it is based on micro data of the NTPs to understand the impact of BRM on realizing benefits.

Research Importance

The National Transformation Programs (NTPs 2021-2025) were initiated in Saudi Arabia with the goal of creating a more diversified and sustainable economy, improving the efficiency of the public sector, and promoting social equity. These initiatives have been successful in achieving these goals and are positively impacting the Saudi economy and its citizens. However, the success of these initiatives is contingent upon buy-in from all stakeholders and will require continued commitment and effort from the government, private sector, and citizens in order to fully realize their benefits. BRM and NTP have both been implemented for a variety of different projects in Saudi Arabia. However, there needs to be more research into the effectiveness of these two approaches in maximizing the value of their investments. (National Transformation Program, n.d.)

Research Questions

BRM has been examined in numerous studies in relation to various variables. Since there are few studies investigating the relationship between Benefits Realization Management (BRM) and National Transformation Programs (NTP) in Saudi Arabia, the researcher identified the following research questions:

- 1- What is the meaning of Benefits Realization Management (BRM).
2. What is the meaning of National Transformation Programs (NTP).
3. What are the Benefits Realization Management (BRM) and National Transformation Programs (NTP) can bring to Saudi Arabia?
4. What is the value being realized through the themes of the National Transformation Program?

Literature review

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has developed an integrated vision of 2030 and established mega projects. One of the most important projects is the NEOM project. The NEEM project is a large-scale mixed-use city planned in the Northwest region of the kingdom. The city is expected to be the sustainable model for the cities of the future. It is a \$500 billion project, which will be developed by the private sector in collaboration with the government. The Neom megaproject seeks to transform the Red Sea coast of the Kingdom into a cutting-edge hub and tourist destination. It aims to create a world-class sustainable city with advanced facilities to draw talent from around the world and become a top tourist destination (*Saudi Crown Prince's \$500bn Neom High-Tech Hub Project Seeks International Interest*, 2022).

Source: <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2037661/business-economy>

The National Transformation Program is an ambitious program that aims to create a model society by transforming all aspects of Saudi Arabian life based on five key pillars: economic transformation, governance transformation, social development, public sector transformation, and individual development. In the Literature review, the researcher will cover the (7) themes of the National Transformation Program (NTP) and its relationship with Benefits Realization Management (BRM). In order to accomplish Benefits Realization Management (BRM), distinct and precise objectives must be outlined, as well as reliable measurement metrics to monitor the outcomes and identify benefits (*Zalando PMO Blog - Understanding Benefits Realization and Why It Matters*, 2022). The National Transformation Program has precise objectives and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each of its seven themes. Here, the researcher evaluates related reports and studies to observe the benefits that have been attained.

Benefits Realization Management (BRM)

Benefits Realization Management (BRM) is a comprehensive process that enables an organization to realize the benefits of its programs, projects and investments. It ensures that the business gets the most value out of these programs while managing the risks associated with them. BRM is a best practices approach that many organizations have adopted to ensure that their programs and projects deliver the promised benefits to the business and that these risks are appropriately

managed throughout the program lifecycle. (*Benefits-Realization-Management-Framework*, n.d.). The Benefits Realization Management process identifies, plans, delivers and sustains a project's benefits through four distinct points (Identity- Plan- Deliver- Sustain). In each stage of the BRM process, specific objectives are laid out and assessed to ensure that the project is on track. As the project moves through the BRM phases, there should always be a feedback loop that helps the project team identify opportunities for improvement and make course corrections as needed. Benefits realization management (BRM) is a fundamental approach in business management. It is a systematic approach that enables organizations to identify, track, and realize the benefits of strategic investments. BRM consists of four interdependent activities: designing benefits, mapping them to assets, monitoring performance, and actively managing for value. By assessing the value of investments in strategic initiatives and addressing them with this integrated approach, organizations can ensure that their investments are successful and beneficial. BRM can benefit organizations in both the short and long term, by helping them achieve better results, foster collaboration, and realize greater return on investments. With this comprehensive approach to monitoring, evaluating, and managing business results, organizations are able to optimize their resources and make more informed decisions, leading to increased efficiency and better overall business performance. (*Zalando PMO Blog - Understanding Benefits Realization and Why It Matters*, 2022).

Source: (Benefits Realization and Benefits Management, n.d.)

The National Transformation Program (NTP)

The Saudi National Transformation Program (NTP) is an ambitious government initiative that aims to drive the modernization of key sectors across the Kingdom. As part of the NTP, various initiatives have been launched across different sectors of the economy to transform these sectors in line with Vision 2030. To support this transformation, several programs are being implemented to help businesses transform their operations and seize the opportunities arising from the changing environment. However, to successfully deliver these programs, the organizations must undertake proper planning to ensure that the benefits are delivered, and the risks and costs are adequately mitigated. The BRM approach will enable these organizations to effectively implement their plans and maximize the value derived from their programs while minimizing the associated risks (Gouider, 2018).

National Transformation Program (NTP) consists of a set of programs and initiatives, which aim to improve the socio-economic conditions in Saudi Arabia. These programs are divided into four pillars - 'Institutional Reform', 'Economic Diversification', 'Social Development' and 'Educational Development'. The first pillar focuses on promoting and institutionalizing good governance principles and improving government efficiency at all levels. The second pillar aims to broaden the base of the Saudi economy by diversifying the economic base away from oil dependency and toward private sector-led growth. (Alasiri and Mohammed, 2022).

The third pillar aims to develop the skills of the Saudi workforce through improved education and vocational training. Finally, the fourth pillar aims to develop the technical and professional capabilities of Saudi nationals in order to equip them with the skills needed to drive the future economic growth and social development of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. These four pillars represent the main objectives of the NTP and are also the cornerstone of the new Vision 2030 Strategy for the Saudi economy. One of the ways in which the Kingdom can achieve its objectives is through the implementation

of effective and effective project management methodologies and tools. The benefits realization management (BRM) framework is a project portfolio management tool that has been successfully used in a number of large-scale programs around the world and that could prove extremely useful for the implementation of the NTP in Saudi Arabia. (Mitchell and Alfuraih, 2018).

The Kingdom's Vision 2030 program entered its next phase in 2021 with the National Transformation Program. Saudi Arabia's ambitions and capabilities were reflected in reorganizing and adding Vision Realization Programs during this phase. Therefore, NTP's plan was updated, and new initiatives were developed to meet the new strategic objectives. The second phase of NTP's work included 7 themes and 34 strategic objectives as well as seven entities leading the effort. (Mitchell & Alfuraih, 2018).

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Achieve Government Operational Excellence			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Percentage of the Ministry of Justice's services provided electronically	30% 2015	81.16% 2021	85.45% 2021
Beneficiary Satisfaction with Judicial Services (%)	72% 2018	76.74% 2021	81% 2021
Percentage of civil service employees engagement	68% 2017	74% 2021	80% 2021
Kingdom's rank in Corruption Perception Index (CPI) issued by Transparency International	57 2017	50 2021	52 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit from the Government Operational Excellence (Theme One)?

National Transformation Program (Government Operational Excellence) and Benefits Realization Management (BRM) are two concepts that are essential in creating successful transformations in government.

In Saudi Arabia, government operational excellence is being leveraged to capitalize on key benefits and gain competitive advantages. According to Al-Ghamdi (2015), these improved outcomes include cost containment, improved efficiency, better decision-making and faster response times. Operational excellence is being achieved through the implementation of best practices

for government organizations to ensure that their operations are in optimum working condition. This includes the implementation of data-driven performance metrics, improved process optimization, and enhanced customer service. By improving their operational excellence, the government in Saudi Arabia is able to realize savings in costs, resources, and staff time while also improving overall performance and customer service. Ultimately, this will result in superior services and products, as well as improved quality of life in the country. National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure Government Operational Excellence through BRM.

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Ensure Sustainability of Vital Resources			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Number of licenses issued to trade in wildlife and their products	2,035 2018	2,600 2021	4,169 2021
Kingdom's score at Environmental Performance Index (EPI) [Ⓢ]	44 points 2020	45.65 points 2022	44 points 2020
Percentage of environmentally licensed industrial facilities	42% 2019	59% 2021	59.1% 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Through (**Theme One**), the government sector will be developed by removing obstacles. Additionally, it will enhance the regulatory environment so citizens can trust government services. A realization management initiative addresses these opportunities and lays the foundation for Saudi Arabia's transformation. Through the provision of high-quality services that are affordable and accessible, the government aims to improve the quality of life for its citizens. (*Initiatives and Services Introduced by Saudi Arabian Government Authorities to Support Businesses during the Emerging COVID-19 Pandemic*, n.d.).

Example of the realized benefits, the "NAGIZ" Platform has undergone several improvements, including new features designed to speed up litigation procedures. This results in the Platform allowing all judicial requests to be submitted electronically, saving time and effort. The digitized real estate transaction and registration documents surpassed 81.9 million. The largest in the Middle East and open twenty-four hours a day, the Central Digitization Center of the Kingdom processed the documents. In the following seven regions of the Kingdom: Riyadh, Eastern Region, Najran, Al Qassim, Mecca, Al-Madina, Aseer, and Northern Borders, five programs were run to improve the behavioral skills and competencies of public sector employees. For employees of the public sector, the "ETHRAI" platform offered a number of online conferences and courses. Using a national distance learning program called "ETHRAI", public sector employees will be more effective

because they can easily advance their knowledge and skills.

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of Ensuring Sustainability of Vital Resource (Theme Two)

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, under **the leadership of Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman Al Saud** has embarked on a large-scale program of economic reform aimed at achieving economic development and social transformation in the country. The NTP has implemented several measures to ensure the sustainability of vital resources. These include the development of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, and the promotion of energy efficiency. The NTP has also implemented measures to reduce water consumption and improve water management. Additionally, the NTP has implemented measures to reduce air pollution and improve air quality. (*Leadership Message*, n.d.).

National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure Sustainability of Vital Resource through BRM.

- Reduce all types of pollution.
 - Safeguard the environment from natural threats.
 - Protect and rehabilitate natural landscapes.
 - Ensure development and food security.
 - Ensure sustainable use of water resources.
- (*Environmental Protection in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia*, n.d.).

Ensure Sustainability of Vital Resources			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Area of rehabilitated natural vegetation	22,668 hectares 2015	47,500 hectares 2021	60,065 hectares 2021
Accuracy of forecasting and early warning of meteorological hazards (sandstorms and floods) 3 days prior	60% 2017	72% 2021	71.7% 2021
Percentage of natural reserves to the Kingdom's total area	4.33% 2017	15.696% 2021	16.124% 2021
Percentage of essential medicines available at the local market	90.83% 2015	95.2% 2021	95.99% 2021
Percentage of food lost and waste ^o	33.1% 2018	33.1% 2022	-
Reuse rate of treated wastewater	13.55% 2015	21% 2021	22.32% 2021
Percentage of sanitation services coverage for the population ^o	56.65% 2019	59.6% 2021	59.09% Q3 of 2021
Duration of water strategic storage for urban utilization ^o	1.35 days 2018	2.32 days 2021	2.12 days 2021
Supply continuity rate	14 hours/day 2017	20 hours/day 2021	20.47 hours/day 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

The NTP has also implemented measures to protect and conserve natural resources. These include the establishment of protected areas, the promotion of sustainable forestry, and the implementation of measures to reduce soil erosion. Additionally, the NTP has implemented measures to reduce waste and promote recycling. The NTP has also implemented measures to promote sustainable agriculture. These include the promotion of organic farming, the introduction of new technologies, and the implementation of measures to reduce the use of pesticides and fertilizers. Additionally, the NTP has implemented measures to reduce the use of water for irrigation and to promote the use of water-saving technologies (*Ways Saudi Arabia Is Looking to Save Water*, 2019).

The NTP has also implemented measures to promote sustainable tourism. (*Towards Saudi Sustainable Tourism*, n.d.). These include the promotion of eco-tourism, the development of sustainable tourism infrastructure, and the implementation of measures to reduce the environmental impact of tourism. Overall, the NTP has implemented a wide range of measures to ensure the sustainability of vital resources. These measures have helped to reduce the country's dependence on oil, create jobs, increase economic growth, and improve the quality of life for citizens. The NTP has also helped to protect and conserve natural

resources, promote sustainable agriculture, and promote sustainable tourism. (Pethybridge, 2021).

Example of the realized benefits, approximately 3.5 million tons of grain will be stored by the Saudi Grains Organization at Yanbu Commercial Port, becoming the organization's fourth access point on the Red Sea. The Saudi Arabian government and India have signed an agreement to establish a free economic zone. Among the foods that will be stored and imported into Saudi Arabia is rice, which will support and secure the country's main food sources. One project aimed at promoting and strengthening the agricultural sector was launched that encourages and supports citizens in learning agriculture skills. In this project, youth are taught how to reduce pressure on natural resources and implement correct agriculture practices to combat the challenges currently facing the agricultural sector. With an operating rate of just 2.27 kilowatt-hours/m³, the Saline Water Conversion Corporation (SWCC) was given a Guinness World Record for being the world's lowest energy-consuming desalination plant. Through reverse osmosis technology in their mobile desalination units, which have a capacity of 5,000 m³/day, SWCC set a record for electricity consumption in the desalination industry. (*SWCC Achieves a New Guinness World Record for the Lowest Water Desal Energy Consumption*, 2021).

Source: (SWCC Achieves a New Guinness World Record for the Lowest Water Desal Energy Consumption, 2021).

Source : (www.vision2030.gov.sa-Green Riyadh, n.d.)

Another very important and outstanding realized benefit, on 19 March 2019, Green Riyadh is one of the four mega projects launched by **King Salman Bin Abdelaziz**, with the goal of making Riyadh one of the world's top 100 most livable cities. The project will involve planting 7.5 million trees across the city, in gardens, parks and public spaces, as well as along streets, roads and utilities lines. It will also include green belts, empty lots, and valleys. (Green Riyadh, n.d.). 7.5 million trees will be planted across Riyadh city in 3,330 neighborhood gardens, 43 parks, 9,000 mosques, 6,000 schools, 64 universities, 390 healthcare facilities and 1,670 public facilities. Trees will also line 16,400 kilometers of streets and roads, 2,000 car parking sites, 1,100 kilometers of green belts including utilities lines (pylons, oil pipelines,

etc.), 175,000 plots of empty land and 272 kilometers of valleys.

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of Social Empowerment and Non-Profit Sector Development (Theme Three)

Non-profit and social empowerment organizations have become increasingly significant in Saudi Arabia in recent years, creating a larger space for public participation and offering a range of direct and indirect services to the population. These organizations contribute significantly to the capacity building of local communities, providing them with access to resources, knowledge and information, and to the economic and social development of the country. (Dagres, 2021).

Social Empowerment and Non-Profit Sector Development			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
The Percentage of private sector's contribution from total social expenditure ^o	1.19% 2018	1.32% 2021	1.35% 2020
The Percentage of large companies adopting social responsibility programs ^o	30% 2018	44% 2021	51.3% 2020
Percentage of development expenditures from total non-profit sector expenditures ^o	21% 2015	70.2% 2021	69.4% 2020
Beneficiaries' satisfaction with the services of non-profit organizations	73% 2019	80% 2021	94.1% 2021
Number of Volunteers in the Kingdom	22,924 volunteers 2015	360,000 volunteers 2021	484,251 volunteers 2021
Number of volunteering opportunities available to the Kingdom's population	9,578 opportunities 2015	160,000 opportunities 2021	242,805 opportunities 2021
Economic value of volunteering in the Kingdom per capita	0.6 SAR 2015	17 SAR 2021	52.58 SAR 2021
Percentage of Non-Profit Organizations' Contribution to GDP ^o	0.2% 2015	0.49% 2021	0.54% 2020
Percentage of Growth in Number of Non-Profit Organizations	0% 2015	56.11% 2021	88% 2021
Percentage of Specialized Non-Profit Organizations that Support Development Priorities	26% 2015	52% 2021	68.50% 2021
Percentage of Non-Profit Sector's Personnel out of the Total Workforce ^o	0.13% 2017	0.35% 2021	0.39% 2020
Beneficiaries' Satisfaction with Social Services	68% 2019	70% 2021	81.30% 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure Social Empowerment and Non-Profit Sector Development. (*Empowering Nonprofit Sector Aims to Raise GDP: Al-Ghafis Says | Ministry of Human Resource and Social Development*, n.d.).

- Empower citizens through the welfare system Improves effectiveness and efficiency of welfare system
- Encourage volunteering (Matic et al., 2012).
- Enhance businesses' focus on their social responsibilities
- Support growth of non-profits sector

- Empower non-profits organizations to create a deeper impact

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has made great strides in recent years to improve the country, including their proactive approach to encouraging volunteering. (Matic et al., 2012). Offering various initiatives for individuals, as well as businesses and non-governmental organizations, Saudi Arabia has taken steps to make volunteering an easier process. The result of these initiatives has been an increase in volunteers, making it easier for citizens to contribute to societal and individual development (Dagres, 2021).

Labor Market Accessibility and Attractiveness			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Women Ratio in Managerial Positions (Middle & Senior)	28.6% 2017	29.4% 2021	39% Q3 of 2021
Economic participation rate of Saudi females (over the age of 15)	17% 2017	31.4% 2021	34.1% Q3 of 2021
Woman's share in the labor market (from the overall Saudi labor force)	21.2% 2017	28% 2021	33.6% Q3 of 2021
Percentage of workers among all people with disabilities who can work	7.7% 2016	11.7% 2021	12.2% First half of 2021
Percentage of Establishments Complying with Occupational Safety and Health Law	15% 2019	61% 2021	69.1% 2021
Compliance Rate with the Expatriate Workers' Wage Protection System	50% 2017	72% 2021	72.5% Q3 of 2021
Improvement Percentage of Expatriates Working Conditions	39.7% 2020	42.5% 2021	55.4% 2021
Kingdom's Rank in IMD World Talent Rankin	29 2019	34 2021	38 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Example of the realized benefits. The donations made on the National Donations Platform helped more than 2.4 million people. On “WAQFY”, contributions totaling more than 75 million SAR were received. The target goal of 70% was exceeded, with the satisfaction rates of social service recipients rising to 81.30 percent. Saudi Arabia's recent regulations on businesses have encouraged a focus on their social responsibilities and the impact they have on their communities. By elevating this importance, the country is advocating for responsible practices, which could have a positive long-term impact on the economy. Business The NTP has also implemented measures to protect and conserves can not only help local communities by creating jobs, but they can also further environmentally goals and sustainability, both of which can help increase the overall profitability of their operations. A commitment to social progress is beneficial for not only the larger society but also for businesses, as it enables them to maintain their competitive edge and purpose. Saudi Arabia's proactive approach to corporate social responsibility is a model for countries around the world.(Total Number of Donations to Ehsan Crosses 2.9 Billion, 2023).

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of Labor Market Accessibility and Attractiveness (Theme Four)

National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure Labor Market Accessibility and Attractiveness as below:

- Increase women participation in the labor market

- Enable integration of people with disabilities in the labor market
- Improve working conditions for expats
- Source relevant foreign talent effectively

Example of the realized benefits. The National Transformation Program (NTP) in Saudi Arabia has realized the benefit of labor market accessibility and attractiveness in a number of ways. The NTP has implemented a number of initiatives to make the labor market more accessible and attractive to both employers and employees. (Impact of the National Transformation Programs on the Life Quality of the Saudi Woman, 2021). First, the NTP has implemented a number of reforms to make the labor market more accessible. These reforms include the introduction of a unified labor market, the establishment of a unified labor law, and the introduction of a unified labor market system. These reforms have made it easier for employers to access the labor market and for employees to find jobs. The unified labor market system has also made it easier for employers to find qualified employees and for employees to find suitable jobs. (El-Katiri, 2016).

Second, the NTP has implemented a number of initiatives to make the labor market more attractive. These initiatives include the introduction of a minimum wage, the introduction of a national employment service, and the introduction of a national labor market information system. These initiatives have made it easier for employers to find qualified employees and for employees to find suitable jobs. The minimum wage has also made it easier for employers to attract and retain qualified employees. From the total labor force, there

Source: (Rivera, 2021)

Digital Transformation			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Number of Initial Digital Business Models	10 2019	70 2021	100 2021
Number of Participants in Digital Awareness-Activities	0 2019	360,000 2021	403,997 2021
Kingdom's Rank in the UN EGD ¹	44 2016	38 2022	43 2020
Savings Resulting from Digital Government Initiatives	0.62 billion 2019	2.21 billion 2021	2.21 billion 2021
Measurement of Government Digital Transformation	45% 2019	50% 2021	48.62% 2021
Digital Transformation Maturity for Key Government Services	60% 2016	84% 2021	84% 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

was an increase in the proportion of women in the workforce. By the end of 2021, there will be more than 114,000 flexible and remote work contracts. QURRAH, which offers assistance in childcare centers, has benefited more than 6,645 women. Certificates for MOWAAMAH were given to more than 1,634 establishments. The certificate proves that the organization gives disabled people an equal chance at employment and makes sure that their needs are met at work. The Training and Leadership Orientation for Women Cadres initiative attracted more than 1,045 female trainees.(Rivera, 2021).

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of Digital Transformation (*Theme Five*)

The National Transformation Program in Saudi Arabia has seen first-hand the benefits of digital transformation.

Through investments in technology and modern digital solutions, the country has been able to refine its existing capabilities, supercharge productivity, and close the gap between public and private sector. (*Saudi Arabia's Digital Government Stays Ahead of the Curve*, n.d.).

National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure the capacity of Digital Transformation as below:

- Develop the digital economy.
- Develop the e-Government.

Example of the realized benefits. The National Transformation Program (NTP) in Saudi Arabia has realized the immense benefits of digital transformation. The NTP is a government-led initiative that seeks to diversify the economy, create jobs, and improve the quality of life for citizens. Digital transformation is a key

component of the NTP, as it enables the government to leverage technology to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of its operations. By embracing digital transformation, the NTP has been able to reduce costs, increase productivity, and improve customer service. One of the most significant benefits of digital transformation for the NTP is the ability to streamline processes and reduce paperwork. By digitizing documents and automating processes, the NTP has been able to reduce the amount of time and resources spent on manual tasks. This has allowed the NTP to focus more on strategic initiatives. (*Labor, Employment and Human Resource Development in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia*, n.d.).

The NTP has also been able to improve customer service by leveraging digital technologies. By using digital tools such as chatbots and automated customer service systems, the NTP has been able to provide faster and more efficient customer service. This has resulted in improved customer satisfaction and loyalty.

In addition, the NTP has been able to use digital technologies to improve the accuracy and speed of data analysis. By leveraging big data and analytics, the NTP has been able to gain insights into customer behavior and preferences, which has enabled them to make more informed decisions. In recent years, Saudi Arabia has made substantial strides in digital transformation. Initiatives such as Vision 2030, the National Transformation Plan, and the Saudi Arabia Digital Economy Strategy have granted the country access to new technologies, such as cloud computing and 5G mobile networks. Saudi Arabia has begun to recognize the value of digital transformation and the various benefits it can bring to its economy. Over the years, the country has invested significantly in digital infrastructure and developed initiatives to spur innovation in advanced digital technologies. Through the use of digital transformation, the country is creating new opportunities and increasing efficiency in the public and private sector, creating new digital jobs and increasing productivity. In addition, the country is taking advantage of the potential of digital transformation in areas ranging from healthcare to digitizing government services. Digital transformation is also helping to reduce the number of manual tasks that need to be performed, saving time and money and streamlining processes. As a result, Saudi Arabia is continuing to embrace digital transformation as a way of driving innovation and economic growth. In conclusion, the National Transformation Program in Saudi Arabia has been able to realize the benefits of digital transformation to increase efficiency and reduce costs

throughout various organizations. From the use of cloud services to other automation initiatives, the NTP has been able to equip its citizens with the necessary tools and resources to boost economic growth and provide a better quality of life for its citizens. In essence, the NTP has been able to take advantage of digital transformation to propel the country forward and set a strong foundation for the future of Saudi Arabia. (*Large-Scale Digital Initiatives Transforming Saudi Arabia's Economy*, 2022). In line with Vision 2030 and the National Transformation Program 2020, Saudi Arabia has been a leader in implementing the latest technologies in the region. The National Strategy for Data & AI outlines Saudi Arabia's goal of attracting SR75 billion (\$20 billion) in investments in data and AI. According to a PwC report, Saudi Arabia is set to have the largest economic benefit from AI during that period, with AI contributing over \$135.2 billion to its economy. The Middle East is expected to receive 2 percent of the total global AI benefits in 2030. (*Saudi Bets Big on AI Developing Local Capabilities to Disrupt Economy*, 2022). In the 2021 Digital Riser Report published by the European Center for Digital Competitiveness, the Kingdom came in second place among G20 nations. To promote the adoption of digital innovation in the Kingdom and further create an environment suitable for digital business, including digital start-ups and investors, 5 memorandums of understanding between the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology and various venture capital firms were signed. To give participants the chance to compete in a number of challenges that tech start-ups frequently face, a digital challenges program was established.

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of Private Sector Empowerment (Theme Six)

The introduction of private sector empowerment in Saudi Arabia has created positive economic benefits for the region and its citizens. The Saudi Arabian National Transformation Program, or NTP, has effectively demonstrated the considerable benefits of private sector empowerment. (*Labor, Employment and Human Resource Development in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia*, n.d.). By creating a more attractive and supportive environment for entrepreneurs and private businesses, government regulations have been simplified and foreign investment has increased significantly. National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure the capacity of Private Sector Empowerment as below:

<p>Leading Entity</p> <p>وزارة التجارة Ministry of Commerce</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Enable the development of the retail sector › Enhance ease of doing business › Strengthen communication channels with citizens & business community › Grow SME contribution to the economy
<p>Leading Entity</p> <p>وزارة الاستثمار Ministry of Investment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Attract foreign and local investments
<p>Leading Entity</p> <p>وزارة الاقتصاد والتخطيط Ministry of Economy & Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Enhance businesses' focus on the sustainability of the economy
<p>Leading Entity</p> <p>Human Resources and Social Development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Grow productive family's contribution to the economy

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Private Sector Empowerment			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
Business community's satisfaction with government communication channels	90% 2020	90.4% 2021	94% 2021
Distance to Frontier (Ease of Doing Business Report)	61% 2017	81% 2021	Report discontinued
Volume of productive families sales supported by Social Development Bank	360 million 2016	10,545.85 million 2021	10,725.68 million 2021
Number of productive families benefiting from Social Development Bank's services	3,000 beneficiaries 2016	74,374 beneficiaries 2021	83,667 beneficiaries 2021

Source: (Annual-Ntp-Report-2021-En.Pdf, n.d.)

Example of the realized benefits, to build up the Kingdom's private sector and make sure they were assigned to the right government agencies, more than 750 economic reforms were carried out. Government agencies can respond to public comments and feedback on proposed laws relating to economic and development affairs before they are approved through the Public Consultation Platform ISTITLAA, which promotes a secure and stable business environment. There are now 9 additional Saudi Business Center locations. Petrol pumps, scales, and home meters are now included in the National Metrology program TAQYEES, an initiative to ensure the accuracy of measuring instruments used in commercial operations. The Kingdom's implementation of intellectual property protection has been improved, and the effectiveness and caliber of the services offered have increased.

As a result, growth within the private sector has been robust and has helped diversify the Saudi Arabian

economy. Furthermore, increased employment opportunities within the private sector have contributed to a decrease in unemployment. Saudi Arabia attracts foreign and local investments to realize the expected benefits, such as employment opportunities, economic growth, technology transfer, and technological innovations. According to the latest official data released by the Saudi Central Bank (SAMA), foreign investment increased by 16% to SAR 2.256 trillion in Q2 2021 compared with SAR 1.951 trillion in Q1 2021. Foreign investments grew by 6%, or SAR 126.3 billion, compared to the first quarter of 2021. As a key enabler of Vision 2030, Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman launched the National Investment Strategy (NIS) on October 11, according to data compiled by Argaam. As part of the strategy, net foreign direct investment will reach SAR 388 billion by 2030, and local investment will reach SAR 1.7 trillion (ArgaamPlus, n.d.).

Source: (ArgaamPlus, n.d.)

A fundamental component of realizing these benefits is the adoption of structured processes and systems to manage the implementation, integration, execution, and success of each program. The Saudi government encourages the private sector to adopt such tools and invest in them to achieve the desired results and minimize potential risks. Saudi Arabia develops promising local companies into regional and global leaders to realize the expected benefits of Vision 2030. Creating a local SME ecosystem is crucial to the success of this transformation program. It is supported by the BRM program, which focuses on helping companies realize their benefits. In addition, the NTP plays a crucial role in enabling SMEs to grow and become sustainable by assisting them with market access and other necessary resources. The government of Saudi Arabia is developing its local SME sector as a critical driver of economic growth and prosperity. (*Labor, Employment and Human Resource Development in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia*, n.d.).

Saudi Arabia grows productive families' contribution to the economy. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to provide the right environment and tools for productivity enhancement. The public sector needs to provide a supportive environment for business as well as identify those interventions that will make the most impact in realizing the Vision 2030 strategy. One tool that has the potential to achieve both objectives is Benefits Realization Management (BRM). Saudi Arabian families have made great contributions to their national economy through diligent work ethics, sensible budgeting, and investments. As the Saudi economy has developed, Saudi families have become increasingly productive and important to the country's economy. Saudi women have made a number of strides in recent years, expanding their access to the workforce, including newly established jobs and increased positions in the public and private sector. The Productive Families Initiative launched by the Government of Saudi Arabia has improved the economic position of the country, with more families now able to participate in the nation's economy.

This initiative has focused on empowering individuals to work from home and capitalize on their skills, allowing

multiple individuals from the same household to create a part-time or full-time business. As a result, more and more families can now offer goods and services that contribute to the increased economic activity of the nation, as well as support their own livelihoods. These positive changes in the economy have been a boon for Saudi families, bolstering the nation's overall economic growth. (*Financing Productive Families*, n.d.). Saudi Arabia has implemented various policies and regulations that focus on the sustainability of the economy. For example, the Saudi Arabia Vision 2030 initiative embraces the concept of sustainability, emphasizing the importance of entrepreneurship, decreasing public-sector dependency, and diversifying the economic, industrial, and agricultural base ("The Strategic Vision for the Kingdom 2030: A Vision for the Future of Saudi Arabia"). Saudi Arabia has also enforced export policies and restricted investments abroad to support its economy better and protect against uncertain global economic conditions. By focusing on these and other policies, Saudi Arabia has created an environment in which small and large businesses can build upon the existing infrastructure and foster sustainable economic growth. (*Saudi Exports Initiatives*, n.d.).

How the NTP in Saudi Arabia realized the benefit of the Development of Economic Partnerships (Theme Seven)

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has historically been an important geopolitical force in the Middle East and beyond. The country, which is a member of the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries and the Gulf Cooperation Council, is now looking to broaden its economic partnerships with other countries. As Saudi Arabia seeks to transition away from its traditional reliance on oil, it is increasingly focusing on developing strong economic ties with other countries in order to improve its overall economic situation. (Arabia, 2022).

National Transformation Program determined key objective to realize the expected benefits with main KPIs to ensure the development of Economic Partnerships as below.

Leading Entity

وزارة الاستثمار
Ministry of Investment

- › Push forward the GCC integration agenda
- › Develop economic ties with global partners
- › Develop economic ties with the region beyond GCC
- › Develop promising local companies into regional and global leaders
- › Support national champions to consolidate their leadership globally

Development of Economic Partnerships			
KPI	Baseline	Target	Actual Value
FDI flows	17.11 billion 2019	42 billion 2021	65 billion Q3 of 2021

Example of the realized benefits, The Kingdom will continue to improve its ties with key partners and countries worldwide to create new economic opportunities and stimulate growth in both domestic and international markets. Saudi Arabia will strengthen its bilateral relations with the United States, China, the European Union, and other key nations to support its economy's continued development and provide more excellent opportunities for its citizens. Through improved trade relations and enhanced international partnerships, the Kingdom will work to create a more dynamic business environment that will support the long-term growth of the Saudi economy. It will also take steps to streamline government bureaucracy and make more resources available to the private sector to help spur economic growth in the country. By developing stronger relationships with foreign governments and businesses worldwide, the Kingdom will continue to play a pivotal role in the global economy in the years to come. The Saudi Vision 2030 Plan emphasizes the development of the country's infrastructure and aims to build new infrastructure in areas such as energy, transportation, healthcare, and education. These initiatives will play a key role in enhancing Saudi citizens' quality of life and helping attract foreign investment to the country. As a result, the government will see a significant increase in its economic output in the years ahead. (*Saudi Arabia's Rapid Infrastructure Development*, n.d.). The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and businesses from various Saudi sectors have signed a

number of agreements and memoranda of understanding for projects with a combined value of more than 3 billion USD. 25 prominent Saudi companies met with a delegation from Uzbekistan led by the deputy prime minister and the minister of investment and foreign trade. To discuss the difficulties Saudi businesses face in the Egyptian market and the best ways to address them, 22 meetings between Saudi and Egyptian businesses were held. An economic delegation from the Republic of Sudan met with various Saudi ministers and businesses and participated in workshops to discuss ways the Kingdom can collaborate with and invest in Sudan. A Kazakhstani business delegation and 25 top Saudi companies met several times to talk about ways the Saudi companies can grow and look for new business opportunities. Several prominent and promising national businesses attended a Saudi-French Investment Forum that was held. 27 agreements were signed as a result of the Forum between Saudi and French businesses.

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is striving to ensure future growth and development of its nation, and that includes growth and development in the sports sector. To this end, they have made a bold move that demonstrates their commitment to their goals: the signing of one of the world's most renowned players, Cristiano Leonardo, to their football team. Such a step signifies their ambition to be a top-tier competitor in international football (Ebrahim, 2023).

Source: (Ebrahim, 2023)

CONCLUSION

The National Transformation Program in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia achieved many benefits through the actual implementation of many initiatives during the period 2021 to 2025. Indeed, until the date of January 2023, it has gained considerable achievements in the seven themes that were identified in the National Transformation Program and have introduced several initiatives that will be implemented in the coming period. This integrated approach is expected to lead to better outcomes and enhanced efficiency, especially where programs are coordinated across departments and agencies. The BRM process will continue to help the authorities implement the National Transformation Program effectively. It is important to note that the program is not just about the physical transformation of existing facilities but, more importantly, is about changing the mindset and culture within organizations to ensure that they are truly geared towards improved service delivery and improved outcomes for their clients.

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